

Cybersecurity in Agriculture: balancing risks, costs & benefits

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

10 APRIL 2025

Introduction

On 10 April 2025, the [European Association for Innovation in Rural Development \(AEIDL\)](#) organised a webinar on [“Cybersecurity in Agriculture: balancing risks, costs & benefits.”](#) Organised in the framework of the [CODECS Knowledge Accelerator](#), the event served as an opportunity for experts to share insights on the state of digital agriculture and the importance of ensuring secure digitalisation in this new age of farming.

As highlighted by **Serafin Pazos-Vidal** (Senior Expert in rural development at AEIDL) in his introduction, the purpose of the event was to discuss vulnerabilities of digital farming, discussing its risks, costs and benefits, and presenting a number of insights from [CODECS](#) and beyond.

He also highlighted the timeliness of this session, in light of the ongoing review of the [Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\)](#), and the **importance of security** in the current discussions. The trade-offs required and the potential investments from both public policy and private actors, including farming operators, make this a particularly relevant topic.

ORGANISER:

10 APRIL 2025

ONLINE

74 PARTICIPANTS
(research, public authorities, advisors, business, rural communities, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

30 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND
RECORDING [HERE](#)

Cite as: Ntabhashe, M., Iglesias, M., Pazos-Vidal, S., (2025). CODECS Knowledge Accelerator: Cybersecurity in Agriculture: balancing risks, costs & benefits. Highlights' report.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15267172

If you see this icon, click to see the presentation

If you see this icon, click to see the video

Cybersecurity in agriculture: Insights from Research

Angelica Marotta Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Angelica Marotta, Cybersecurity Researcher at the [Massachusetts Institute of Technology](#), opened her presentation by highlighting how **increased digitalisation and automation in agriculture have made the sector more vulnerable**. Today, agriculture is ranked the **seventh most targeted industry for cyberattacks**. She highlighted how alarming it is that an essential and traditionally low-tech sector as agriculture is becoming a cyber target. This reflects how far the digital shift has gone and how much is at stake if we do not secure it.

“Security is no longer just a technical issue; it is systemic and it shapes trust and resilience.”
Angelica Marotta, MIT

Dr. Marotta presented multiple examples of cyberattacks from the last few years. A ransomware attack targeting a Brazilian-based meat processing company **disrupted supplies across several countries**, including the USA, Canada, and Australia. Additionally, the Dole ransomware attack, which was a 10.5 million dollar attack on the company, **temporarily halted fruit and vegetable supplies across North America**. As these attacks were ransomware, they posed threats not only to **personal data** (such as employee information) but also **disrupted entire systems**. The consequences spread quickly and go beyond financial losses, **affecting production timelines, food access, and even animal welfare**.

Moreover, Dr. Marotta pointed out issues that are often overlooked, such as **regulatory risks**. Regulatory risk is not usually a priority in companies, which tend to focus on security and technology. However, when it comes to assessing compliance within their environments, many issues emerge. Hence, **governments are trying to respond to these alarming threats**, especially in agriculture.

In the **United States**, the [Farm and Food Service Security Act of 2025](#) and the [CISA Agricultural Sector Guidelines](#) were introduced in response to the growing wave of cyberattacks targeting the agriculture and food sectors. These regulations

aim to **ensure minimum security standards** for agricultural technology. It is also important for small companies to establish their own **compliance and security measures**, with an emphasis on **reporting cyber incidents**.

In the **European Union**, the [Digital Operational Resilience Act](#), [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#), and the [Cyber Resilience Act](#) are important reference points for agriculture. However, the real challenge is not only creating new rules but also **harmonising them**, making them more comprehensive, and ensuring they keep up with what is happening in the field.

Although cyberattacks in agriculture are usually thought to target large companies, **small farms can also be affected, and they are often more vulnerable**. Dr. Marotta gave the example of a small local farm in Switzerland where a ransomware attack **paralysed the automated milking system**. As a result, cows were not milked, which resulted in the death of one pregnant animal. The total loss was \$10,000, which is a relatively small, but enough to push the farmer to the brink of shutting down.

Cyberattacks in agriculture aren't just economic. They affect animal welfare, food safety, communities, and families. When we zoom out from these incidents, clear lessons emerge:

- **No one is too small to be targeted.** Small farms are often more vulnerable because they lack security resources and are more likely to pay quickly to resume operations.
- **Automation can create fragility.** If digitalisation is not built on a secure foundation, it increases vulnerability.
- **General technology security advice is not adapted to agriculture.** Best practices must be tailored to the specific needs and risks of the sector. Collaboration and harmonisation are fundamental to ensure secure digital farming.

Figure 1. Key lessons learned from cybersecurity incidents in agriculture

CODECS Perspective on Cybersecurity Challenges

Gianluca Brunori
University of Pisa & CODECS Coordinator

Gianluca Brunori, Full Professor of Food Policy at the [University of Pisa](#) and CODECS Coordinator, highlighted the “**digital utopia**” that agriculture is currently facing. It is the dream of a farming sector full of sensors, where everything is monitored, and any variable can be predicted. **This utopia envisions connected farmers surrounded by devices, software, sensors, databases, and people.**

Since the beginning of the CODECS project in 2022, and even before with the [DESIRA project](#) (Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts on Rural Areas, from 2019-2023), the possible risks of digitalisation have been highlighted. **At first, the projects did not focus on cybersecurity risks, but recent events have shown how important this topic is.** For instance, considering the current geopolitical tensions, it is now understood that satellite systems could be disrupted for various reasons. As a result, CODECS must now consider scenarios that were previously not taken into account, or were seen as highly unlikely.

The project has adopted a **systemic approach to the digitalisation of agriculture**. Indeed, the costs of digitalisation are not only economic but also social and environmental.

1. Economic costs

Direct costs of cyberattacks include investment in technology and infrastructure, staff training, compliance, certification, and insurance. **Indirect costs may arise from the damage caused by cyberattacks**, as highlighted by Dr. Marotta in her presentation. Professor Brunori gave the example of a vertical farming system where all operations are controlled by a computer. If that system is hacked, the whole production could be lost. At the same time, there is a risk of **data breaches**, which can damage a company's **reputation and market position**.

2. Social costs

When analysing the social costs of cyberattacks, **food security** is key. For instance, if 1000 chickens are killed in a cyberattack, what does that mean for **food availability and rural livelihoods**? Such situation can also affect farmers' stress levels and reduce trust in digital technologies. In addition, it can lead to **less openness and less data sharing**, as Maj Vilfan will highlight in his presentation on the risks of open data. Data sharing is vital for the digital economy, but if farmers are afraid of cybersecurity threats, **the benefits of digitalisation may be slowed down**. Finally, cybersecurity risks could also **widen the digital divide** between those who can afford protection and those who cannot.

3. Environmental costs

One major environmental risk of cyberattacks is the possibility of hackers **poisoning the soil or crops** on a farm where spraying is controlled digitally. There are also indirect environmental costs, such as **pollution**. In addition, there are **trade-offs between environmental protection and economic costs**. These challenges raise important questions about how to address digitalisation in terms of environmental impact. Additionally, a **lack of openness and data sharing could also limit the ability of digitalisation to support sustainability**.

CODECS aims to address all these aspects at the socio-ecological system level. **Secure and inclusive digital ecosystems can make a big difference**. Professor Brunori stressed that digitalisation should not be left to market forces, nor to regulation alone. **While regulation is essential, policies and strategies are needed at both the territorial and national levels, along with strong public investment in security**. Finally, **risk assessments** are also necessary to better respond to cyber threats.

Figure 2. Multidimensionality of digital agriculture

Open data in agriculture: opportunities and threats

Maj Vilfan
University of Ljubljana

Maj Vilfan, PhD Researcher at the [University of Ljubljana](#), focused his presentation on the risks associated with **open data**. He began by distinguishing between two types of open data: **data that is made public by choice, and data that becomes public due to poor data sharing practices**. This second situation is particularly dangerous, as just like in the military, the first phase of any cyberattack is **reconnaissance by gathering information**, before moving on to the actual attack.

With the rise of agricultural digitalisation, more and more data related to farming is becoming public. **This means that attackers can gather information without hacking, just by using what is already available online**. This could include personal data about individuals and their families, social media profiles, or more technical information such as the type of devices, seeds, or pesticides used on a farm. It could even include business-related information: for instance, by accessing a company's invoice online, an attacker could learn how much the company is willing to pay for a product and use this information to **manipulate the market**.

Mr. Vilfan shared several **demonstrations** showing how easily confidential information can be found online without using illegal methods. He introduced the [Open source intelligence \(OSINT\) Framework](#), a tool that catalogues all publicly available data that can be accessed using non-intrusive methods. In one example, **he found the web server** of an American pesticide company, along with its IP address, operational details, and open ports. He also showed how, in under two minutes, he was able to use **Google search to find the login credentials** for the webdisk of a Slovenian farm that sells produce online.

He also shared the **John Deere OSINT case**, where a cybersecurity researcher, using only publicly available data, was able to uncover vulnerabilities in John Deere's agricultural software and equipment. The researcher found **sensitive data** such as user accounts and farm equipment details and even accessed remote-control functions for tractors, all **without hacking or using illegal tools**.

Mr. Vilfan also demonstrated how, using **Google dorking** (advanced search techniques using specific Google parameters), he was able to find sensitive data such as the names, contact details, and positions of farm workers, and even Google Drive links to documents labelled "confidential", all **openly accessible via a basic search**.

Agriculture is only starting to digitise, but already relies on a mix of open and semi-public data. **This makes it vulnerable to different types of attacks**, including phishing emails, denial-of-service attacks, or price manipulation based on market intelligence. Therefore, cyberattacks don't only pose technical challenges, they also affect business models and market fairness. As Professor Brunori noted earlier, the impacts of cyber threats are **multidimensional**.

How do we address this? Mr. Vilfan proposed a **three-step approach**:

- 1. Data classification:** Based on the [NIS2 Directive](#), there is a need to organise all data produced by a company or sector according to its **confidentiality, integrity, and availability**. This helps identify critical data that should not be shared publicly.
- 2. Employee training and data-sharing protocols:** Once data is classified, companies must establish **clear protocols** for how different types of data can be shared, and employees should be trained on how to follow these rules.
- 3. External security audits:** These audits have two components. First, **"Google audits"**, where a firm checks what can be found online about a company using tools like Google and AI. Second, audits of the **dark web**, to identify if any sensitive company data is being shared or sold. Knowing this allows companies to take preventive action and improve their cybersecurity practices.

How to ensure secure digitalisation for all farmers?

Nevena Alexandrova-Stefanova
Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)

Nevena Alexandrova-Stefanova, Innovation Officer at the **Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)** highlighted the growing cybersecurity challenges faced by smallholder farmers in developing countries, where digitalisation is accelerating despite limited resources and pre-existing vulnerabilities. These include not only cyber threats but also physical security issues, economic pressures, and food insecurity.

Dr. Alexandrova-Stefanova approached the issue through a **foresight lens**, using **future scenarios to explore how cybersecurity can either strengthen or weaken agricultural systems**. She presented two contrasting scenarios: one where secure digitalisation fosters sustainable, inclusive agri-food systems driven by open innovation, and another where inadequate cybersecurity leads to distrust, systemic instability, and increased exploitation of vulnerable communities.

In the **positive scenario**, digital infrastructure, blockchain, and participatory governance empower farmers and equalise power dynamics across the value chain. In contrast, the **negative scenario** sees farmers exposed to ransomware attacks, digital scams, and data breaches, ultimately eroding trust in technology and institutions.

She stressed that cybersecurity must be seen as a **foundational layer** in agricultural transformation, not just a technical add-on. Without it, even the most promising digital innovations may backfire or deepen existing inequalities.

Dr. Alexandrova-Stefanova introduced a **policy framework** developed by the FAO that focuses on three key pillars:

- **Policy and governance**, including baseline security standards and multilateral coordination on data rights and protection.
- **Foresight and risk assessment**, using scenario modelling to anticipate cyber threats and their impact on food security and rural livelihoods.
- **Human-centred approaches**, such as behavioural science tools to understand farmers' digital habits and training needs.

She also provided concrete examples of **innovative policy responses to ensure secure digitalisation of agriculture**:

- **Shared security infrastructure** through cooperatives that distribute the cost and management of cybersecurity tools.
- **Government support mechanisms** like cybersecurity subsidies, vouchers, and tax incentives for vulnerable farmers.
- **Security-as-a-service models**, offering subscription-based solutions tailored to rural agricultural contexts, such as mobile security packages.

The FAO official concluded her presentation by emphasising **the importance of equity in digital transformation**. Secure digitalisation is not only about access to technologies, it is about **ensuring that all farmers are protected, empowered, and included** in the digital future of agriculture;

Figure 3. FAO's foresight approaches to anticipate future threats and building resilient systems

Group discussion

Moderated by Serafin Pazos-Vidal (AEIDL)

The discussion highlighted the urgent need to ensure that **cybersecurity frameworks are accessible and relevant to farms of all sizes**, especially smallholders and digitally vulnerable actors. Several speakers noted that while large agribusinesses may already have the resources to respond to cybersecurity threats, small and medium-sized farms risk being excluded without targeted technical and financial support.

Speakers emphasised the importance of **collective approaches** – such as **cooperatives, shared infrastructure, and value chain collaboration** – to reduce the individual burden on farmers. There was consensus that digitalisation cannot be left to market and regulatory forces alone; instead, public investment and policy coordination are needed to build inclusive and resilient digital ecosystems.

The discussion also underlined the growing threat of ransomware and data exposure through open-source intelligence (**OSINT**). Participants learned that these attacks are increasingly driven by profit motives and are made possible by poor data practices—something that even small farms are not immune to. External audits and improved data classification protocols were proposed as essential steps toward mitigation.

The exchange closed with a **call for harmonised regulatory frameworks and stronger international cooperation**. Panellists encouraged participants to engage in cross-sector collaboration and use foresight methodologies (such as those shared by the FAO) to better anticipate future risks and shape inclusive digitalisation strategies.

Conclusions & next steps

Merveille Ntabuhashe
AEIDL

In conclusion, **the webinar highlighted the critical role of cybersecurity in the sustainable digital transformation of agriculture**. The session demonstrated that securing digital agriculture is not merely a technical challenge but a complex, multidimensional issue with economic, social, and environmental implications.

Key takeaways included the need to recognise agriculture as a form of critical infrastructure, the importance of regulatory harmonisation, and the value of collective approaches to ensure that smallholder farmers are not left behind.

The discussions underscored the growing threat of ransomware, data breaches, and open-source intelligence exploitation, especially in sectors with limited digital maturity. In response,

actionable strategies were shared, including capacity-building, scenario-based foresight, improved data-sharing protocols, and tailored cybersecurity support for vulnerable actors.

In her closing remarks, **Merveille Ntabuhashe**, project manager of **AEIDL** reminded participants that the webinar took place in the context of the **CODECS Knowledge Accelerator**, a platform committed to supporting knowledge exchange and collaboration on sustainable digitalisation. The **KA community** invites stakeholders across agriculture, research, and policymaking to contribute to shared learning, exchange best practices, and co-develop inclusive strategies for the future of digital farming.

